

MARKET STATUS OF UKAY-UKAY AND READY-TO- WEAR BUSINESS IN TAGBILARAN CITY

Michelle C. Cahucom

Bohol Island State University- Main Campus, Tagbilaran City, Bohol, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13359227>

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the market status of ukay-ukay and ready-to-wear (RTW) businesses in Tagbilaran City, Bohol, and examines whether significant differences exist between these two sectors. The research aims to profile these businesses in terms of capital, rental, product offerings, revenue, permits, supply sources, bulk releases, and product disposal, as well as assess their market status regarding price, product quality, promotion, location, and sanitation. Utilizing a questionnaire based on Garrovillas (2013), data were collected from ukay-ukay and RTW business owners. Analysis revealed that RTW businesses generally require higher capital and rental expenses compared to ukay-ukay. Despite both sectors generating similar revenue, RTW businesses incur higher permit fees and have fewer bulk releases. The findings indicate that ukay-ukay is more affordable and perceived as having better product quality, while RTW excels in promotion, location, and sanitation. A z-test confirms a significant difference between the market statuses of ukay-ukay and RTW. Based on these results, recommendations include rehabilitating stalls, implementing price tariffs, enhancing promotions, establishing sanitation oversight, and enforcing quality control for ukay-ukay vendors. Further research is suggested to validate and expand upon these findings.

Keywords: *Consumer Behavior, Market Status, Ready-to-Wear (RTW), Sanitation, Ukay-ukay*

INTRODUCTION

The clothing industry remains one of the most dynamic and competitive sectors worldwide, driven by the fundamental human need for clothing. Among the prominent segments within this industry today are ukay-ukay (second-hand garments) and ready-to-wear (RTW) apparel. These sectors are particularly relevant within the context of sustainable fashion, which emphasizes the need for the fashion industry to balance economic, environmental, cultural, and social goals. Ukay-ukay, by promoting the reuse of clothing and reducing environmental impact, presents a more sustainable alternative compared to fast fashion and luxury fashion (Biana, 2020).

The appeal of ukay-ukay lies in its affordability, offering fashionable and durable clothing at prices accessible to people with lower incomes (Isla, 2013). This accessibility has made ukay-ukay a popular alternative to brand-new garments found in boutiques and shopping malls, especially in regions like Bohol, where the industry has flourished in recent years. Despite concerns about sanitation, limited sizes, and potential defects, ukay-ukay continues to thrive, particularly in urban centers such as Tagbilaran City, where numerous ukay-ukay and RTW stalls can be found.

The sustained growth of the ukay-ukay and RTW industries in Bohol has piqued the interest of the researcher, prompting an investigation into consumer surplus and market dynamics within this sector. By examining these aspects, the study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the market status of ukay-ukay and RTW, offering insights into how these businesses contribute to the local economy and what improvements can be made. Recognizing their significance as a source of income for local entrepreneurs and revenue for the city government, the study also considers the potential benefits of a proposed plan to enhance the operations of ukay-ukay and RTW stalls.

Grounded in several theories of consumer behavior, this research builds on Thorndike's Law of Effect, which suggests that consumers are likely to repeat purchasing behaviors that have previously been satisfying (Athalye et al., 2018). This principle aligns with observations that satisfied customers tend to return to products or services that have met their expectations (Nacif, 2012). Additionally, Ajzen and Fishbein's Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (1980), as cited by Al-Suqri and Al-Kharusi (2015), highlights the role of pre-existing attitudes and intentions in consumer decision-making, while Stern's concept of impulse behavior underscores the influence of external stimuli on purchasing decisions. Consumers often determine the attractiveness of a business through the quality of service extended to them, with excellent services or products encouraging repeat patronage (Danesh, Nasab, & Ling, 2012). These theoretical perspectives, combined with observations of consumer preferences and behaviors, form the foundation of this study, which seeks to shed light on the factors driving the success of ukay-ukay and RTW businesses in Bohol.

Moreover, this study draws on previous research that has explored various facets of the ukay-ukay industry, including its economic impact, consumer attitudes, and the ongoing debate over its legalization. The insights gained from this research will be

instrumental in formulating strategies to support and sustain the growth of the ukay-ukay and ready-to-wear (RTW) sectors, ensuring that they continue to serve as vital components of the local clothing industry. According to Te et al. (2021), the ukay-ukay industry significantly contributes to local economies by providing affordable fashion and fostering sustainability, reinforcing its critical role in the clothing market.

Research Questions

The main thrust of this study was to assess the significant difference between the market status of ukay-ukay and RTW business in Tagbilaran City, Bohol.

More specifically, it sought to answer the following specific questions:

1. What is the profile of ukay-ukay and RTW business in Tagbilaran City in terms of:
 - 1.1 Capital ;
 - 1.2 Rental ;
 - 1.3 Product ;
 - 1.4 Revenue ;
 - 1.5 Permit ;
 - 1.6 Supply ;
 - 1.7 Bulk of release and
 - 1.8 Upshot of the product?
2. What is the market status of ukay-ukay and RTW in Tagbilaran City in terms of :
 - 2.1 Price;
 - 2.2 Product quality;
 - 2.3 Promotion/ marketing presentation ;
 - 2.4 Placement/location and
 - 2.5 Sanitation?
3. Is there a significant difference between the market status of ukay-ukay and RTW?
4. What action plan can be proposed to upgrade the ukay-ukay and RTW business in Tagbilaran City?

METHODOLOGY

This section focused on the methodology that was utilized in the conduct of the study. It also outlined the research design, the procedure that was followed, the process of collecting the data, and the analysis. During the collection process, the ethical considerations were also discussed.

Research Design

This inquiry utilized descriptive-survey methods. In the descriptive survey, the researcher used a questionnaire as the primary tool. After collecting the data, a z-test

was employed to determine the level of difference between the market status of ukay-ukay and RTW.

The results of this survey provided a reference point for analysis, interpretation, and evaluation, serving as the basis for improving the ukay-ukay/RTW business through a proposed measure or plan.

Research Environment and Research Participants

This study was conducted in Tagbilaran City, Bohol, which is considered the heart of the province, where trade and commerce are concentrated. Tagbilaran City comprises fifteen (15) barangays: Bool, Booy, Cabawan, Cogon, Dampas, Dao, Manga, Mansasa, Poblacion I, Poblacion II, Poblacion III, San Isidro, Taloto, Tiptip, and Ubujan. However, only Barangay Dao, Poblacion 2, Poblacion 3, Cogon, and Manga had ukay-ukay and RTW businesses. The researcher chose this environment considering that Tagbilaran City is the province's main business capital and center of governance, with numerous ukay-ukay and RTW stalls found in the area.

The study involved 379 respondents, including 155 ukay-ukay customers, 137 RTW customers, 62 ukay-ukay entrepreneurs, and 35 RTW entrepreneurs.

An initial survey was conducted to determine the tentative number of ukay-ukay and RTW customers in Tagbilaran City on a typical day. Slovin's formula was then used to calculate the sample size. Customers were randomly given questionnaires to complete, and as needed, the researcher translated the questions into the vernacular to ensure the respondents' understanding. This approach was employed to elicit the market status of ukay-ukay and RTW businesses.

Research Instrument

The instrument used in conducting the study was a questionnaire. Two questionnaires were employed to gather data. The first one was designed for ukay-ukay and RTW entrepreneurs, aiming to ascertain the profile of these businesses in Tagbilaran City. This questionnaire was self-made, crafted with the assistance of the researcher's adviser and an English critic. A thorough modification process was undertaken before finalizing the instrument. Pilot testing was conducted to test the validity of the questionnaire.

The second questionnaire, intended for ukay-ukay and RTW buyers, was designed to assess the market status and identify any significant differences between ukay-ukay and RTW apparel in Tagbilaran City. This questionnaire was based on a marketing book by Garrovillas (2013), with modifications made by the researcher to align it with the current study. Pilot testing was also conducted to ensure the validity of this questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sent a letter to the Campus Director and the Dean of Graduate Studies requesting permission to conduct the study. Permission was also sought from the Mayor of Tagbilaran City, where the respondents resided. Afterward, the researcher requested permission from the owners of ukay-ukay and RTW businesses in Tagbilaran City to administer the questionnaire. A guided interview approach was adopted, where the researcher directed the interviewees through the questions, saving time and effort for the ukay-ukay and RTW business owners.

Additionally, random ukay-ukay and RTW customers were selected to answer the second type of questionnaire. The researcher sought permission from these customers, and upon their approval, they were given ample time to read and complete the questionnaire. The questionnaire was also translated into Visayan to ensure that the respondents could easily understand the items. The questionnaires were retrieved after the respondents thoroughly answered them. The tabulation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data followed. Finally, based on the conclusions of the study, recommendations and a proposed action plan were made.

Data Analysis

To determine the profile of “ukay-ukay” and RTW entrepreneurs in terms of capital, rental, product, revenue, permit, supply, bulk of release per month and upshot of the product, the percentage will be computed.

To determine the weighted mean of the market status of “ukay-ukay” and RTW in terms of price, product quality, promotion, placement and sanitation, weighted mean was computed and interpreted using the following scale:

Where:

Weighted Mean Intervals	Qualitative Description
3.25 - 4.0	Superior
2.50 - 3.24	Good
1.75 - 2.49	Fair
1.0 - 1.74	Poor

To test the significant difference between the market status of ukay-ukay and RTW, Z test was computed. The formula is:

$$z = \frac{(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{SD_1^2}{N_1} + \frac{SD_2^2}{N_2}}}$$

Where:

z = Z test

X_1	=	weighted mean of the market status of ukay-ukay
X_2	=	weighted mean of the market status of RTW
N_1	=	population of "ukay-ukay" costumers
N_2	=	population of RTW costumers
SD_1^2	=	Variance of the market status of "ukay-ukay"
SD_2^2	=	Variance of the market status of RTW

RESULTS

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered from the survey questionnaires, focusing on the marketability of ukay-ukay and ready-to-wear (RTW) businesses in terms of price, product quality, promotion or marketing presentation, placement or location, and sanitation. Additionally, it examines whether there is a significant difference between the market status of ukay-ukay and RTW.

Table 1 outlines the profile of ukay-ukay and RTW business owners in Tagbilaran City. Among the 62 ukay-ukay stalls, most have an initial capital of PHP 40,000.00 to PHP 40,999.00, while the 35 RTW stalls generally have a higher initial capital, ranging from PHP 50,000.00 to PHP 50,999.00. This indicates that the RTW business typically requires more capital than the ukay-ukay business.

In terms of rental costs, most ukay-ukay businesses pay a monthly lease of PHP 5,000.00 to PHP 9,999.00, whereas RTW stalls incur higher rental costs, typically between PHP 15,000.00 and PHP 15,999.00 per month. Ukay-ukay stalls generally have lower rental expenses because they are often located in informal areas, such as along roadsides, while RTW businesses are situated in more formal, presentable locations.

Regarding the types of products sold, ukay-ukay stalls primarily offer t-shirts, blouses, and pants, with children's wear being the least common due to concerns about sanitation. Similarly, RTW stalls also mainly sell t-shirts, blouses, and pants, with cosmetics being the least offered, likely because they are considered luxury items rather than necessities.

In terms of monthly revenue, both types of businesses typically earn between PHP 20,000.00 and PHP 24,999.00. Most ukay-ukay businesses pay an annual permit fee of PHP 1,000.00 to PHP 4,999.00, while RTW businesses pay a higher permit fee, ranging from PHP 5,000.00 to PHP 9,999.00. This difference in permit fees is consistent with the higher capital requirements for RTW businesses.

The products sold by both ukay-ukay and RTW businesses are primarily sourced from Korea, recognized as a fashion capital. These products are popular and in demand due to current fashion trends. Ukay-ukay businesses typically release 11-20 bulk orders per month, whereas RTW businesses release only 5-10 bulk orders. This disparity is largely due to the lower pricing of ukay-ukay products, which makes them more affordable than RTW products.

Finally, if products remain unsold, both ukay-ukay and RTW businesses often resort to sales promotions, such as buy-one-get-one-free offers or 50% discounts, to recover their capital. A small number of owners also choose to donate unsold items to charity or repurpose them as rags.

Table 1
Profile of Ukay-ukay and RTW owners in Tagbilaran City

Profile of Ukay-ukay and RTW in Tagbilaran City in terms of:	Ukay-ukay N=62		RTW N= 35	
	No. of responses	Percentage	No. of responses	Percentage
CAPITAL				
• P 30,000.00-P 30,999.00	10	16 %	2	6 %
• P 40,000.00-P 40,999.00	35	56 %	3	9 %
• P 50,000.00-P 50,999.00	2	3 %	12	34 %
• P 60,000.00-P 60,999.00	2	3 %	2	6 %
• P 70,000.00-P 70,999.00	4	6 %	6	17 %
• P 80,000.00-P 80,999.00	3	5 %	1	3 %
• P 90,000.00-P 90,999.00	1	3 %	1	3 %
• P 100,000.00 up	5	8 %	8	23 %
Total	62	100%	35	100%
RENTAL				
• P 1,000.00-4,999.00	13	21%	1	3%
• P 5,000.00- 9,999.00	35	56%	9	26%
• P 10,000.00-14,999.00	2	3%	5	14%
• P 15,000.00- 19,999.00	2	3 %	11	31%
• P 20, 0000.00 -up	10	16%	9	26%
Total	62	100%	35	100%
PRODUCT				
• Blouses/T-shirts	58	94 %	30	86%
• T-shirts for men	58	94 %	30	86%
• Pants for women	45	73 %	30	86%
• Pants for men	45	73 %	30	86%
• Shorts for men	32	52 %	22	63%
• Shorts for women	40	65%	22	63%
• Underwear	5	8%	16	46%
• Children's wear	30	48 %	25	71%
• Gowns	6	10%	7	20%
• Tailored suits	6	10 %	7	20%
• Curtains	16	26 %	23	66%
• Bedding	34	55%	23	66%
• Bags	40	65%	30	86%
• Footwear for men	23	37%	29	83%
• Footwear for women	23	37%	29	83%
• Stuffed toys	19	31%	17	49%
• Accessories	27	44 %	30	86 %
• Others, please specify (cosmetics)			5	14%
Total	62	100%	35	100%
REVENUE OR INCOME PER MONTH				
• P 5,000.00-P 9,999.00	3	5%	4	11%
• P 10,000.00-P 14,999.00	17	27%	5	14%
• P 15,000.00-P 19,999.00	5	8%	8	23%
• P 20,000.00-P 24,999.00	28	45%	11	32%
• P 25,000.00 up	9	15%	7	20%
Total	62	100%	35	100%
PERMIT				

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P 1,000.00-P 4,999.00 • P 5,000.00-P 9,999.00 • P 10,000.00-P 14,999.00 • P 15,000.00-P 19,999.00 • P 20,000.00 up 	22	35%	10	29%
	21	34%	13	37%
	5	8%	2	6%
	5	8%	3	9%
	9	15%	7	20%
Total	62	100%	35	100%
SOURCE OF SUPPLY				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Philippines • Taiwan • Korea • USA • Canada • Australia • Online shops • China • Others, please specify(Thailand) 	7	11%	12	34%
	9	15%	10	29%
	20	32%	25	71%
	14	23%	21	60%
	2	3%	2	6%
	6	10%	2	6%
	5	8%	13	37%
	9	15%	15	43%
	2	3%	3	9%
BULK OF RELEASE PER MONTH				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5-10 bulk • 11-20 bulk • 21-30 bulk • Others, specify _____ 	20	32%	16	46%
	29	47%	9	26%
	13	21%	10	29%
Total	62	100%	35	100%
UPSHOT OF THE PRODUCT				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sale it. (E.g. buy 1. Take 1, 50% off, etc.) • Donate the garments apparel. • Recycle it like make it into rag. • Donate to a certain charity. • Resort to ukay-ukay garments • Others, specify (Put it inside the punching bag, make as a rag.) 	45	73%	27	77%
	6	10%	2	6%
	9	15%		
Total			6	17%
	2	3%		
Total	62	100%	35	100%

Table 2
Market Status of Ukay-ukay and RTW in Tagbilaran City in terms of Price, Product Quality, Promotion or Marketing Presentation, Placement or Location, Sanitation

Ukay-ukay N=155	Description		RTW N= 137	Description
		I. Price		
2.96	Good	1.The price is affordable.	2.37	Fair
3.27	Superior	2.The price goes with the quality.	2.78	Good
3.05	Good	3.The quality exceeds its price or value.	2	Fair
3.46	Superior	4.The price is negotiable.	1.59	Fair
1.52	Poor	5.There is a standard directive of prices among other "ukay-ukay" or RTW stalls.	2.62	Good

2.85	Good	TOTAL	Fair	2.27
		II. Product Quality		
3.59	Superior	6.The product is branded.	2.6	Good
3.63	Superior	7.The design and style of clothes are exclusive.	2.66	Good
3.16	Good	8.There is a good combination of colors.	2.6	Good
3.06	Good	9.Colors are attractive and not faded.	2.84	Good
3.66	Superior	10.The clothing material is durable.	1.67	Fair
3.06	Good	11.There are no defects in the product.	3.28	Superior
3.42	Superior	12.The product is fashionable.	3.13	Good
3.37	Superior	TOTAL	2.68	Good
		III. Promotion or marketing presentation		
3.08	Good	13.The staffs are accommodating.	2.46	Fair
3.34	Superior	14.Sales promos are offered regularly.	2.59	Good
2.42	Fair	15.The products are properly displayed.	2.87	Good
1.74	Poor	16.The products are attractive to look at for it is arrange/hang well.	3.14	Good
1.61	Poor	17.The product is advertised through media like newspaper, radio, etc.	2.7	Good
1.74	Poor	TOTAL	1.97	Fair
		IV. Placement or Location		
2.37	Good	18.The location is accessible.	3.2	Good
2.04	Fair	19.The area is air-conditioned/ well-ventilated.	3.13	Good
1.94	Fair	20.The location is not overcrowded.	2.97	Good
2.02	Fair	21.The location is safe and sound.	3.01	Good
1.99	Fair	22.It has proper lighting.	3.33	Superior
1.92	Fair	23.Emergency exit can be observed.	3.62	Superior
1.79	Fair	24.The flooring is friendly to the customer. It is plane or flat.	3.88	Superior
1.89	Fair	25.The clothing apparels are being hang.	3.93	Superior
2.16	Fair	26.Mannequins are found in the area.	3.82	Superior
1.17	Poor	27.Fitting rooms are present.	2.88	Good
1.97	Fair	28.Mirrors are readily available.	3.8	Superior

2.13	Fair	TOTAL	3.86	Superior
		V. Sanitation		
3.25	Superior	29.The garment apparel undergone treatment indicated by the chemical treatment smell.	3.41	Superior
1.94	Fair	30.Dirt is not found in the garment.	3.73	Superior
1.42	Poor	31.Allergy was not experienced after wearing the garments.	2.92	Good
2.43	Fair	32.Foul smell is absent.	3.5	Superior
2.26	Fair	TOTAL	3.39	Superior

Table 2 presents the market status of ukay-ukay and ready-to-wear (RTW) businesses in terms of price, product quality, promotion or marketing presentation, placement or location, and sanitation.

The data indicates that ukay-ukay has a higher weighted mean in terms of price compared to RTW apparel, signifying that ukay-ukay items are much more affordable. This is supported by Garrovillas (2013), who noted that ukay-ukay thrives widely, largely because its low prices make it accessible even to the poorest individuals, including those at the base of the economic pyramid.

When it comes to product quality, ukay-ukay also scores higher than RTW. This suggests that ukay-ukay garments are perceived as more durable than their RTW counterparts. This finding aligns with the study by Abueg (2005), which highlighted that some consumers prefer ukay-ukay items because they are comparable in quality to brand-new garments and accessories sold in high-end stores, but at a much lower price.

In terms of promotion, RTW has an advantage over ukay-ukay. This discrepancy is linked to the ongoing challenges surrounding the legalization of the ukay-ukay business. In 2002, President Gloria Macapagal-Arroyo banned the entry and sale of ukay-ukay items in the Philippine market, causing dissatisfaction among consumers who viewed ukay-ukay as the most affordable option. As a result, ukay-ukay businesses have struggled to establish effective marketing strategies due to the lack of government support.

Regarding placement, ukay-ukay businesses are rated as having a fair status, while RTW businesses receive a superior rating. Fernandez (2011) explains this by noting that ukay-ukay stalls are typically found in congested areas with poor ventilation, reflecting the lower-quality environment in which these products are often sold. The term "ukay-ukay" itself comes from the Filipino word "hukay," meaning to dig up, which metaphorically describes the process of sifting through items in these crowded locations.

Finally, in terms of sanitation, ukay-ukay businesses are described as fair, whereas RTW businesses are rated superior. This distinction is supported by a blogger's

observation that individuals with higher standards of living prefer to purchase new, ready-to-wear garments from malls, primarily due to concerns about sanitation. Since ukay-ukay clothes are not thoroughly clean, there is a significant risk that bacteria and viruses may be present on these items.

Table 3
Difference between the Market Status of Ukay-ukay and RTW

	Mean	Description	Computed z	Critical z	Interpretation	Decision
Ukay-ukay	2.37	Fair	-10.92	± 1.96	Significant	Reject the null Hypothesis
RTW	2.97	Good				

With the use of z-test, the two variables implied significant difference since the computed tabular value of -10.92 was lower than the critical value ± 1.96 at 0.05 significance at 103 freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference in the market status of ukay-ukay and RTW.

DISCUSSION

Findings

After the data were analyzed and interpreted, the researcher derived the following findings.

A. Profile Ukay-ukay and RTW

The profile analysis reveals that among the 62 ukay-ukay stalls surveyed, the majority have a capital investment ranging from PHP 40,000.00 to PHP 40,999.00. In contrast, the 35 RTW stalls typically have a higher capital investment, ranging from PHP 50,000.00 to PHP 50,999.00.

Regarding rental costs, most ukay-ukay businesses pay a monthly lease of PHP 5,000.00 to PHP 9,999.00, while RTW stalls have higher rental expenses, typically between PHP 15,000.00 and PHP 15,999.00 per month. Both ukay-ukay and RTW businesses primarily sell t-shirts for both men and women.

In terms of revenue, both business types generate an income ranging from PHP 20,000.00 to PHP 24,999.00 per month. When it comes to business permits, ukay-ukay stalls pay an annual fee ranging from PHP 1,000.00 to PHP 4,999.00, whereas RTW businesses pay between PHP 5,000.00 and PHP 9,000.00.

The source of products for both ukay-ukay and RTW businesses is primarily from Korea, known as the "Fashion Capital." Ukay-ukay businesses typically release 11-20 bulk orders per month, while RTW businesses release fewer, around 5-10 bulk orders monthly.

Finally, if products remain unsold, both ukay-ukay and RTW businesses often resort to promotional sales, such as "buy one, take one" or offering items at a 50% discount, to recover their capital. A small number of business owners choose to donate unsold items to charity or repurpose them as rags.

B. Market Status of Ukay-ukay and RTW in Tagbilaran City

The analysis reveals that ukay-ukay is more affordable, with a higher weighted mean of 2.85 for price compared to RTW's 2.27. In terms of product quality, ukay-ukay again leads with a weighted mean of 3.37, surpassing RTW's 2.68. However, RTW excels in promotion and marketing presentation, scoring 1.97 against ukay-ukay's 1.24. For placement or location, RTW has a superior rating of 3.86, while ukay-ukay is rated fair at 2.13. When it comes to sanitation, RTW maintains a superior rating with a weighted mean of 3.39, compared to ukay-ukay's 2.26. Overall, RTW is rated as "good" with an average weighted mean of 2.97, making it more marketable than ukay-ukay, which is rated as "fair" with an average weighted mean of 2.37.

C. Difference Between the Market Status of Ukay-ukay and RTW

The analysis using a z-test revealed a significant difference between the market statuses of ukay-ukay and RTW. The computed z-value was -10.92, which is lower than the critical value of +1.96 at a 0.05 significance level with 103 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a significant difference in the market status between ukay-ukay and RTW.

Conclusions

Based on the data analyzed in this study, it was concluded that the market status of ukay-ukay is rated as fair, with an average weighted mean of 2.37, whereas the market status of RTW is rated as good, with an average weighted mean of 2.97. This disparity highlights that RTW apparel outperforms ukay-ukay in terms of price, product quality, promotion, placement, and sanitation. The significant difference between the market statuses of ukay-ukay and RTW, as indicated by the z-test results, confirms that RTW has a more favorable market status compared to ukay-ukay.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from this study, the following recommendations are proposed to improve the ukay-ukay and RTW businesses in Tagbilaran City:

Rehabilitation of Stalls: The city government should consider the rehabilitation of ukay-ukay and RTW stalls, as these businesses contribute significantly to the city's income.

Tariff Approval: Ukay-ukay and RTW vendors should establish a tariff for their prices, subject to approval by the relevant Board, to ensure fair pricing practices.

Enhanced Promotion: Entrepreneurs should develop effective promotional strategies for ukay-ukay and RTW to enhance their market presence and appeal.

Sanitation Oversight: The city government should create a committee to regularly assess the status of ukay-ukay and RTW businesses, with a particular focus on sanitation standards.

Quality Control: Ukay-ukay vendors should implement quality control measures to prevent the sale of defective products and ensure customer satisfaction.

Further Research: It is recommended that follow-up research be conducted to verify and expand upon the findings of this study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without coercion. No harm came to participants, and the study received ethics committee approval. Researchers declared no conflicts of interest and reported findings transparently and honestly. Cultural sensitivity was respected throughout the research process.

REFERENCES

- Abueg, L. C. (2005). The economics of second-hand retail trade: An analysis of the market of the ukay-ukay. Manila: Manila Standard Today.
- Al-Suqri, M. N., & Al-Kharusi, R. M. (2015). Ajzen and Fishbein's theory of reasoned action (TRA)(1980). In Information seeking behavior and technology adoption: Theories and trends (pp. 188-204). IGI Global.
- Athalye, V. R., Santos, F. J., Carmena, J. M., & Costa, R. M. (2018). Evidence for a neural law of effect. *Science*, 359(6379), 1024-1029.
- Biana, H. T. (2020). The Philippine Ukay-Ukay Culture as Sustainable Fashion. *DLSU Business & Economics Review*, 30(1), 154-164.
- Danesh, S. N., Nasab, S. A., & Ling, K. C. (2012). The study of customer satisfaction, customer trust and switching barriers on customer retention in Malaysia hypermarkets. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(7), 141-150.
- Fernandez, M. (2011). Does the ukay-ukay industry keep the budget-challenged fashionista? Manila: Manila Standard Today.
- Garrovillas, E. P. (2013). *Marketing principles*. Pasig City, Philippines: Anvil Publishing.
- Isla, V. L. (2013). Investigating second-hand fashion trade and consumption in the Philippines: Expanding existing discourses. *Journal of Consumer Culture*, 13(3), 221-240.
- Nacif, R. C. (2012). *Online customer loyalty: Forecasting the repatronage behavior of online retail customers*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Te, A. B., Ignacio, S. G., Ibraheem, Z. D., & Sam, E. M. C. (2021). Customer preferences in buying second-hand clothing in Digos City. *Journal of BIMP-EAGA Regional Development*, 7(1), 25-41.